

HOW SOCIAL MASKING INFLUENCE ON INDIVIDUAL WELL-BEING

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ABSTRACT

This research is conducted in order to understand and explain the phenomenon of social making and how it can be related to individual well-being in terms of personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations. The study has been based upon positivist philosophy and hence followed the quantitative paradigm. Subsequently, four individual hypothesis were tested by using two tests Pearson correlation test and Spearman rank correlation test. While applying the both tests, it was found that, the p value in all hypothesis is lesser than 0.05 and correlation coefficient was also found to be lower than 0.5. Hence, there is a positive but weak relationship between personality camouflage and individual well-being. Similarly, there is a positive but weak relationship between controlled freewill and individual well-being. Additionally, there is a significant but weak relationship between external expectations and individual well-being. Subsequently, while testing whether all three independent variables are co-related with individual well-being collectively. It was again realized that, the p value in that case is also less than 0.05 with correlation coefficient showing the similar trend. Hence, ultimate weak relationship has been showcased between all three independent variables (Personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations) and individual well-being.

Keywords: Personality Camouflage, Controlled Freewill, External Expectations, Individual Well-being, Quantitative.

INTRODUCTION

The research has been conducted in order to understand how the social masking has been used by the individuals to achieve their economic, social and even political goals while losing their inner self completely in the process. Social masking has been defined as an act by an individual to hide his/her true and real feelings, emotions, thoughts and by all means their true inner self in order to remain part of the either close or wider social circle or society. It is an endeavor to “fit in” in the society even at the cost of losing one’s inner self completely and even damaging one’s well-being (Chapman et al., 2022). Social masking can also be referred as an in-genuine self of an individual or role-playing

because an individual acts in conformity with the external demands or requirements while suppressing or sidelining one’s own real emotional, physical and mental wishes and desires. On the other hand, Individual well-being is defined as the state in which an individual has become self-content, satisfied with one’s inner true self, feeling control over the internal and external circumstances, positively contributing towards achieving personal goals while experiencing positive relationship with external stakeholders (Ruggeri et al., 2020). However, individual well-being is also connected with the mental health as WHO (world health organization) defined mental health as a state in

which an individual is able to attain his/her maximum potential while tackling with the normal stress and hence contribute positively in the community at large (Scully, 2014). However, Tov (2018) divided individual well-being into two aspects internal and external. He elaborated that, external aspect is related with individual being happy with his/her current state of affairs and life in general. While internal aspect is associated with one's psychological health and if and not, the person is able to attain the maximum efficiency and productivity while enhancing one's cognitive and mental capacities and capabilities. He also added that, individual well-being is an intricate concept and it includes almost everything which is needed by an individual to function and grow effectively and efficiently. Subsequently, Taylor et al., (2014) further explained the concept of individual well-being while dividing into two parts-hedonism and Eudaimonia. While Garcia (2006) mentioned that, hedonistic well-being is mostly connected with one's subjective well-being and how one is feeling (e.g. happy/unhappy) with respect to the external events. However, on the other hand, Eudaimonism is the belief that, an individual must be able to achieve his/her maximum potential while adjusting themselves with the requirements of their immediate environment. It is closely related with the concepts of Maslow's conception of self-actualization (1968), Allport's formulation of maturity (1961).

Hence, this study has concentrated on the notion that how individual well-being can be affected by social masking in the current era. Social masking can be determined possibly through multiple elements like personality camouflaging. Personality camouflaging has been described as an act to hide one's true and original self from others while presenting themselves as a different person/s. This is also done through compensation and assimilation in which individuals either try to find different ways and means in order to hide their original self as much as possible to others or try to assimilate into the society through acting in a way that is not true to their original personality or innate characteristics (Robinson et al., 2020). Social masking may be evaluated through controlled freewill as, controlled freewill is defined as the process in which an individual is unable to exercise his/her freewill due to either lack of

belief in it or finding it in contradiction with one's immediate social, economic or even political objectives or goals. In the similar vein, social masking can also be determined through external expectations as external expectations can impact either positively or negatively on individual well-being. Nyuhuan (2023) in this regard highlighted that, external expectations may arise from different quarters of the society including family, friends, professional colleagues, bosses and etc. and they may impact negatively on individual's happiness, personal growth and development and mental health as well. These all factors may relate with individual well-being in general as they all contribute either positively or negatively towards one's well-being. External expectations may be defined as possible presumption by others that an individual will act or do in a certain way and not otherwise. Therefore, in this research, social masking has been conceptualized through these key variables including personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations in order to evaluate their impact on the individual well-being quantitatively. This research is unique in nature as, it tries to prove that the independent variables chosen are positively co-related with the individual well-being as opposite to the popular notion that, their impact on the overall well-being is negative in nature rather than the opposite.

1.1 Problem Statement

Alartartseva & Barysheva (2015) highlighted in their study that, the individual well-being of most of the folks in the world is in question as, there are multiple reasons behind it and one of them is the lack of understanding regarding what well-being is and how it should be determined. They further mentioned that, a misalignment of human being with their true self and an absence of social environment in which one is able to achieve his/her true potential may be reason of one's ill-being. Rogers et al., (2012) on the other hand rejected the idea that, betterment in objective environment can possibly result in increasing individual well-being, while, they emphasized that, well-being is a subjective matter and individual well-being can be increased through policies, that focus on giving maximum freedom to the folks to make their own decisions, creating conducive social environment and ultimately creating possibilities to achieve one's

true potential. In the similar respect, Ofori & Bell (2020) conducted the study on lecturers' well-being and found that, social expectations negatively impact on the well-being of lecturers in Ghanaian context. Eventually, it has been observed that, individual well-being has become a prevalent phenomenon in the social sciences research, however, its relationship with social masking has not yet been examined by any researcher in the field. Hence, this study has tried to investigate and ponder upon how the social masking can influence on individual well-being either positively or negatively.

1.2 Hypothesis

H1= There is a significant positive relationship between personality camouflage and individual well-being.

H2= There is a significant positive relationship between controlled freewill and individual well-being.

H3=There is a significant positive relationship between external expectations and individual well-being

H4= There is a significant positive relationship between all the independent variables as a whole and individual well-being

2.1 Literature Review

Human flourishing or complete well-being of an individual is the recent topic under consideration, that advocates regarding one's well-being not only through fulfilling the subjective and physical needs and demands of multiple facets but the psychological ones as well (VanderWeele, 2020). González-Hernández et al., (2017) further added that, psychological well-being is more important than any other aspects of well-being as, it provides the necessary emotional health and stability needed to cope with stress in general and achieve the personal goals as well. Klein & Macoun (2024) described social camouflaging as an attempt by individuals to either hide their true feelings, emotions, intentions and etc. or to fit into the social circle or society at large as described by Rauthmann's model (2021). He mentioned that, individuals' outward expressions are actually based on their assessment of the environment around themselves and how they can alter their expressions in order to fit their physical self into the requirements of their immediate

environment. He further explained that, there are three components of that interaction including content, level and consistency and all those are directly proportional to needs of one's environment.

However, Cook et al., (2021) described that, personality camouflaging has somehow become the necessity of social relationships as, the social stereotypes attached to some of the personal and professional relationships have forced the individuals to hide their original personality traits and pretend in order to remain in a personal or professional relationship. Although, Gutiérrez & Valdesoiro (2023) narrated a different understanding of personality camouflaging by highlighting that, personality disorders can also become the consequence of the personality camouflage as when individuals try to survive in an evolutionary environment, which may force them to change their personality traits frequently, then some of them can choose to become narcissist, antisocial and even psychopath in the process. But, even then, surprisingly some of those become famous, gain high status in the society and even reach to the highest hierarchy of their social ladder or profession. This study has hence chosen the personality camouflaging as a predictor to investigate its impact on the individual well-being.

The concept of freewill is quite new in the history of mankind as, the freewill was uncommon for the mankind until the idea of democracy with its tenets emerge on the world horizon. Monroe and Malle (2010) added that, freewill means folks have an unchained ability to choose their course of action without internal and external restraints. Although, Feldman et al., (2014) emphasized that, individuals with maximum freedom to make different choices are freer to make decisions more frequently than otherwise, they linked choice-making with freewill overtly. They further added that, belief in freewill may lead towards self-satisfaction at the end. In addition to that, when one is talking about free-will and satisfaction, the theory of Frankfurt seems to be best one to explain the relationship. Although it was Harry Frankfurt who elaborated the concept of freewill through two levels through his essay in 1971, the first order and second-order desires. He added that, if the same reason is behind the second order of desire derives the first order desire as well means the person has the freewill to

make his/her decision without any inner conflict in place (Norris, 2010). Moreover, Crescioni et al., (2015) found that, the belief in free-will can lead towards multiple positive outcomes including greater gratitude in one's life, more life satisfaction as a whole, lower life stress and setting meaningful goals in one's life. Gooding (2019) added that, freewill is actually linked with one's choice making and that choice making then refer towards one's perceived control over his/her behaviors and actions so, if that freewill is manipulated, it can lead towards impacting one's subjective well-being at the end. Hence, the controlled freewill may have a negative impact on individual well-being. This study has hence chosen the controlled freewill as a predictor to examine its impact on the individual well-being. Didkovskaya & Trynov (2019) on the other hand conducted their study how young chaps in Russia can adopt to different situations in their lives and how it impacts on their overall well-being. They concluded at the end that, social expectations do impact on well-being of young adults in Russia. Dejonckheere et al., (2022) added that, individual well-being is an all-encompassing feature that includes social, economic, emotional and physical well-being hence, individuals lacking in any of these aspects may lack the overall subjective well-being at the end. External expectations may play a role in the individual well-being as, the society may pressurize the individuals to make decisions against his/her will or pretend to be satisfied with the decisions made by the other indirectly. That emotional disturbance can result in the deterioration of subjective well-being of an individual at the end. Alexander et al., (2021) further added that, genuine positive emotions can lead towards individual well-being, hence, if the person is not genuinely happy but, pretends to be happy then their neurophysiological processes don't support their gestures and the overall subjective well-being is compromised in some way. Individuals while making decisions or choices under the influence of multiple social actors actually try to manipulate their true self in-front of others due to the social, economic, political, personal or otherwise constraints.

In addition to that, Yunus et al., (2018) added that, the word personality is taken from Greek word "persona" which referred mask and it was used in dramas of that era. Personality is defined

as a set of characteristics possessed by an individual that reflects his/her cognitive, emotional and natural state in different situations. Hence, the personality trait theories come to the fore and shed light on the multiple personality types including extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness and neuroticism (Erevik et al., 2023). Hence, the individuals while making multiple choices or decisions actually try to use the above mentioned personality masks in order to hide their true self and act according to the requirement of the situation at hand. This all eventually impacts on their well-being as, their true self may not be in conformity with what they have been doing in their respective lives. Therefore, in this study, it would be examined that, how personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations can influence on individual well-being objectively.

3.1 Research Methodology

The research methodology is an overarching mechanism through which research is conducted, it includes primarily how the problem has been approached theoretically and then, how the solution has been found by using single or multiple research designs. The methodology even starts with the problem and ends by finding its solution through single or multiple approaches (Goundar, 2012). Hence, this study has used positivist approach as, the problem has been prevalent in the society but, there is not much theoretical evidence available on the issue at hand. Moreover, the study is quantitative in nature as, the research problem has been approached objectively. The sampling design is non-probabilistic in nature as, the problem is quite general but unique in nature hence, it is quite impossible to use the probabilistic sampling design for this study. Pandey & Pandey (2015) defined judgmental sampling as a method of sampling in which, a researcher decides either based on some criterion or simple intuition that, the member of the targeted population would be able to provide valuable insights on the research problem at hand objectively. Hence, the researcher chooses only those members who are deemed to be fit as a respondent of a research study under consideration. In this regard, this study has used judgmental sampling as, the research problem is quite unique and complex in

nature hence, it is not possible to take the insights of each and every member of the targeted population or even provide the equal chance to become the respondent. The sample size of this study is 100+ and it is considered to be appropriate as, Kline (2005) and Kline (2016) suggested that, less than 100 sample size may not be appropriate for any quantitative analysis. Hence, this study has collected data from more than 120 respondents in order to test the research hypothesis appropriately. The research instrument's reliability was also tested by using

Cronbach's alpha and it was found to be reliable as, the value of Cronbach's alpha was 0.791. Moreover, the respondents chosen were belonged to multiple cadres including full-time students, business and IT professionals and others as well. However, the data is collected mainly from those working at multiple positions in their respective organizations. Then, research data was analyzed through two statistical tests including Spearman's rank co-relation test and Pearson co-relation test and then, at the end linear regression was also used to check the model fit of the study.

4.1 Results

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Gender

What is your Gender?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	56	45.9	45.9	45.9
Female	65	53.3	53.3	99.2
Prefer not to say	1	.8	.8	100.0
Total	122	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that, there are more number of female participants in the study than their counterparts.

Table 2: Age

What is your Age?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-23	30	24.6	24.6	24.6
23-28	45	36.9	36.9	61.5
28-33	26	21.3	21.3	82.8
33-38	16	13.1	13.1	95.9
38-43	5	4.1	4.1	100.0
Total	122	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that, more than 60% of participants were below 30 years of age, it implies that, the young adults of Pakistan filled the surveys.

Table 3: Current Qualification

Which category is most suited to your current degree?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Bachelor (BBA, BS, BA, B.com and etc.)	50	41.0	41.0	41.0
Bachelor (Bachelor of Engineering in Electrical, Electronics, Mechanical, Chemical and etc.)	5	4.1	4.1	45.1
Bachelor (Bachelor in Computer Science, IT, Artificial Intelligence and etc.)	15	12.3	12.3	57.4

Masters' Degree in Business Administration (MBA), Public Administration, Commerce and etc.	36	29.5	29.5	86.9
Masters' Degree in Arts, Humanities or Social sciences or etc.	16	13.1	13.1	100.0
Total	122	100.0	100.0	

The Table no.3 shows that, 57% of participants had bachelor degree of some kind and remaining 43% were more qualified than their counterparts.

Table 4: Current Profession

Which category is most suited to your current profession?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Business executive/Assistant manager/Manager/Senior manager (All business fields) and etc.	27	22.1	22.1	22.1
IT professional/computer programmer/developer/graphic designer/coder and etc.	14	11.5	11.5	33.6
Teaching faculty/Lecturer/Assistant Professor/Associate Professor/Professor and etc.	9	7.4	7.4	41.0
Engineering field/Electrical/Electronic/Mechanical/Telecom/Networking/Software and etc.	9	7.4	7.4	48.4
Freelancer/Content writer/technical field/programming/web development/project management and etc.	9	7.4	7.4	55.7
Media Professional/Anchor/Artists/Communication expert/Digital Marketer/Social media marketer and etc.	4	3.3	3.3	59.0
Government officer/official(Federal, Provincial) in any department	12	9.8	9.8	68.9
Full time student in any field (Business Administration/Public Administration/Media/Pharmacy/Medical and etc.	38	31.1	31.1	100.0
Total	122	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that, more than 30% of respondents were full-time students and more than 20% of them were working as business professionals. However, more than 10% were working for IT or computer profession in one way or another.

Table 5: Research Questions Descriptive Analysis

Research Questions Descriptive Analysis

	I always want to make everyone happy even at the cost of hurting myself emotionally/psychologically	I always try to do things that have greater acceptance in the society even at gaining no self-satisfaction and happiness at the end	I always sacrifice my wishes in order to remain part of the larger or smaller group in the society	I always try to make decisions in keeping in view whether they will be granted conformity by my social circle or wider society	I always try to meet my actions with the expectations of my family, friends, colleagues and etc.	I always try to gain maximum acknowledgment of my decisions from different groups of the society (e.g. family, professional, social institutions and etc.)	I feel physical lethargy due to extensive demands from different groups of the society (e.g. family, professional, social institutions and etc.)	I feel emotionally exhausted due to complying with the wishes and desires of people that are connected to me in one way or another	I feel peace of mind and physically active if the actions being taken by me through my own internalization without any external pressure or expectations
Valid N	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.1066	2.8115	2.5984	2.9344	3.8033	3.3443	3.2951	3.2705	4.1066
Median	3.5000	3.0000	2.0000	3.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
Mode	4.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00
Std. Deviation	1.46478	1.22867	1.15465	1.07363	1.00115	1.20447	1.11109	1.17154	1.05867
Range	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Minimum	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00

The table no.5 shows that, the mean of major questions is 3, that indicates the normality of the data and the standard deviation is also slightly above 1, pointing out that, the data is either equally or normally distributed.

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3.2 Normality of the Data

Fig 1: Normal curve of Dependent Variable

Fig 2: Normal curve of Independent Variables

The above two figures exhibit that, the research data of this study is normal whether in terms of independent variables or dependent variable.

4.1 Results

4.2 Inferential Analysis

H1= There is a significant positive relationship between personality camouflage and individual well-being.

Table 5: Pearson Correlation of Hypothesis 1 ▲ ▲

Hypothesis 1

		Personality. Camouflage	Individual. Wellbeing
Personality. Camouflage	Pearson Correlation	1	.326**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	122	122
Individual. Wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.326**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	122	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6: Spearman's Rank Correlation of Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1

		Personality. Camouflage	Individual. Wellbeing
Spearman's rho	Personality. Camouflage	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
		N	122
	Individual. Wellbeing	Correlation Coefficient	.284**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
		N	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The data shows that, the p value is less than 0.05, which implies the Hypothesis 1 is accepted. Moreover, the correlation coefficient is less than 0.5, indicating that, there is a positive but weak relationship between personality camouflage and individual well-being.

H2= There is a significant positive relationship between controlled freewill and individual well-being.

Table 7: Pearson Correlation of Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis 2

		Controlled. Freewill	Individual. Wellbeing
Controlled. Freewill	Pearson Correlation	1	.259**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.004
	N	122	122
Individual. Wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.259**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	
	N	122	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 8: Spearman's Rank Correlation of Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis 2

		Controlled. Freewill	Individual. Wellbeing
Spearman's rho	Controlled. Freewill	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.233**
		N	.010
	Individual. Wellbeing	Correlation Coefficient	.233**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.010
		N	1.000
	N	122	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above tables show that, the p value is less than 0.05 in above tables, imply that, the Hypothesis 2 is accepted. Moreover, the correlation coefficient in Pearson and Spearman rank tests is less than 0.5, indicating that, there is a positive but weak relationship between controlled freewill and individual well-being.

H3=There is a significant positive relationship between external expectations and individual well-being

Table 9: Pearson Correlation of Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis 3

		External. Expectations	Individual. Wellbeing
External. Expectations	Pearson Correlation	1	.360**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	122	122
Individual. Wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.360**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	122	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 10: Spearman's Rank Correlation of Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis 3

		External. Expectations	Individual. Wellbeing
Spearman's rho	External. Expectations	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.267**
		N	.003
	Individual. Wellbeing	Correlation Coefficient	.267**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.003
		N	1.000
	N	122	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The data shows that, the p value is less than 0.05, which implies that, the Hypothesis 3 is accepted. Moreover, the correlation coefficient is less than 0.5, indicating that, there is a positive but weak relationship between external expectations and individual well-being.

H4= There is a significant positive relationship between all the independent variables as a whole and individual well-being

Table 11: Pearson Correlation of Hypothesis 4 Hypothesis 4

		Independent. Variables	Individual. Wellbeing
Independent. Variables	Pearson Correlation	1	.368**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	122	122
Individual. Wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.368**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	122	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 12: Spearman's Rank Correlation of Hypothesis 4 Hypothesis 4

			Independent. Variables	Individual. Wellbeing
Spearman's rho	Independent. Variables	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.289**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	122	122
	Individual. Wellbeing	Correlation Coefficient	.289**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	122	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above tables show that, the p value is less than 0.05 in above tables, imply that, the Hypothesis 4 is accepted. Moreover, the correlation coefficient in Pearson and Spearman rank tests is less than 0.5, indicating that, there is a positive but weak relationship between independent variables and individual well-being.

Model Fit

Table 13: Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.392 ^a	.154	.132	4.19631

a. Predictors: (Constant), External. Expectations, Personality. Camouflage, Controlled. Freewill

Table 14: ANOVA ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	378.138	3	126.046	7.158	.000 ^b
	Residual	2077.862	118	17.609		
	Total	2456.000	121			

a. Dependent Variable: Individual. Wellbeing

b. Predictors: (Constant), External. Expectations, Personality. Camouflage, Controlled. Freewill

Table 15: Coefficients
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	15.471	2.118		7.303	.000
Personality. Camouflage	.188	.108	.198	1.744	.084
Controlled. Freewill	-.026	.110	-.028	-.236	.814
External. Expectations	.259	.106	.269	2.449	.016

a. Dependent Variable: Individual. Wellbeing
 In the above data, it shows that, the value of R is less than 0.5 indicating that, there is actually a weak relationship as a whole between independent and dependent variables. Similarly, the value of unstandardized beta highlights that, the 18% change in terms of personality camouflage will possibly be appeared on one unit change in individual well-being. However, negative 2 percent change in terms of controlled freewill will possibly be appeared on one unit change in individual well-being implying that, controlled freewill will decrease the individual well-being by 2 percent. Although, almost 26% change in terms of external expectations will possibly be appeared on one unit change in individual well-being. Subsequently, it can be concluded from above information that, there is a mainly positively significant but weak relationship between independent variables and dependent variable.

5.1 Discussion

The research was conducted in order to understand how individual well-being is either positively or negatively affected by three major variables including personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations. The study was actually conducted in line with research works conducted by Cook et al., (2021) who mentioned that, personality camouflaging has somehow become the necessity of social relationships as, social stereotypes attached to some of the personal and professional relationships have forced the individuals to hide their original personality traits and pretend in order to remain in a personal or professional relationship. Similarly, Crescioni et al., (2015) found that, the belief in free-will can lead towards multiple positive outcomes including greater gratitude in one's life, more life satisfaction as a

whole, lower life stress and setting meaningful goals in one's life. Subsequently, Alexander et al., (2021) added that, genuine positive emotions can lead towards individual well-being, hence, if the person is not genuinely happy but, pretends to be happy then their neurophysiological processes don't support their gestures and the overall subjective well-being is compromised in some way. Individuals while making decisions or choices under the influence of multiple social actors actually try to manipulate their true self in front of others due to the social, economic, political, personal or otherwise constraints. The researcher has collected data from more than 120 individuals, as most of them were under 30 and had at least one bachelor degree and were either studying or working for multiple professions including business, IT, teaching, engineering and media. Moreover, the normality of the data was also checked and it was found that, the data is normally distributed.

While asking research questions like whether they can make everyone happy even at cost of hurting myself emotionally/psychologically, exactly 50% agreed with the notion that, they do that act. Similarly, while it was asked that, whether they always try to do things that have greater acceptance in the society even at gaining no self-satisfaction and happiness at the end. 45% of them had shaken their heads in the disagreement of that idea. Similarly, while inquiring whether they always sacrifice their desires and wishes in order to remain part of the larger or smaller group in the society. Majority of the respondents explicitly disagreed with the notion. In addition to that, while asking whether or not they try to gain maximum acknowledgement of their decisions from different groups of the society (e.g. family, professional, social institutions and etc.). In the response to that query, 55% of respondents

nodded their heads in agreement. Moreover, in the final section, while asking whether they feel physical lethargic due to extensive demands from different groups of the society (e.g. family, professional, social institutions and etc.) and whether they feel peace of mind and physically active if their actions are being taken by themselves through their own internalization without any external pressure or expectations. More than half of the respondents happily nodded their heads in agreement of the above notions.

In the final section, four individual hypothesis were tested by using two tests Pearson correlation test and Spearman rank correlation test. While applying the both tests on first hypothesis, it was found that, the p value is 0.02 which is lesser than 0.05, which implies that, the Hypothesis 1 is accepted. However, the correlation coefficient is found to be lesser than 0.5, indicating that, there is a positive but weak relationship between personality camouflage and individual well-being. Similarly, while analyzing the Hypothesis 2, it was found through Pearson correlation test, the p value is 0.04, which is lesser than 0.05 and correlation coefficient is 0.259, which is lesser than 0.5, indicating that, there is a positive but weak relationship between controlled freewill and individual well-being. The similar kind of results were found while applying Spearman rank test on Hypothesis 2. While the third hypothesis was tested by using the two tests, it was found that, the p value is either 0.00 or 0.03, the both are lesser than 0.05, correlation coefficient were either 0.360 or 0.267, both are below 0.5. That implies subsequently that, there is a significant but, weak relationship between external expectations and individual well-being. Additionally, while testing whether all three independent variables are co-related with the individual well-being collectively. It was found that, the p value in that case is also less than 0.05 with correlation coefficient showing the similar trend of lesser than 0.5. Hence, ultimate weak relationship has been showcased between all three independent variables (Personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations) and individual well-being.

Likewise, while applying regression analysis in order to find the model fit, it was found that, the value of R is less than 0.5 indicating that, there is actually a weak relationship as a whole between

independent and dependent variables. Similarly, the value of unstandardized beta highlights that, the 18% change in terms of personality camouflage will possibly be appeared on one unit change in individual well-being. However, negative 2 percent change in terms of controlled freewill has been shown on one unit change in individual well-being implying that, controlled freewill will possibly decrease the individual well-being by 2 percent. Although, almost 26% change in terms of external expectations will possibly appear while applying one unit change on individual well-being. The results of this study explicitly contradict with the conclusions being drawn in the studies conducted by Klein & Macoun (2025), Rauthmann's model (2021) and Dejonckheere et al., (2022).

5.2 Conclusion

The research is conducted in order to understand and explain how, the social masking can influence on individual decision making in terms of personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations. The research is one of its kinds as, it presents a unique and different perspective of the rather general proposition that, social masking harm one's well-being in all aspects. The study was conducted quantitatively by collecting data from more than 100 adults either working or studying in their respective fields. Finally, four individual hypothesis were tested by using two tests Pearson correlation test and Spearman rank correlation test. While applying the both tests on first hypothesis, it was found that, the p value is 0.02 which is lesser than 0.05, which implies that, the Hypothesis 1 is accepted. However, the correlation coefficient is found to be lesser than 0.5, indicating that, there is a positive but weak relationship between personality camouflage and individual well-being. Similarly, while analyzing the Hypothesis 2, it was found through Pearson correlation test, the p value is 0.04, which is lesser than 0.05 and correlation coefficient is 0.259, which is lesser than 0.5, indicating that, there is a positive but weak relationship between controlled freewill and individual well-being. The similar kind of results were found while applying Spearman rank test on Hypothesis 2. While the third hypothesis was tested by using the two tests, it was found that, the p value is either 0.00 or 0.03, the both are lesser than 0.05, correlation coefficient were

either 0.360 or 0.267, both are below 0.5. That implies subsequently that, there is a significant but, weak relationship between external expectations and individual well-being. Additionally, while testing whether all three independent variables are co-related with the individual well-being collectively. It was found that, the p value in that case is also less than 0.05 with correlation coefficient showing the similar trend of lesser than 0.5. Hence, ultimate weak relationship has been showcased between all three independent variables (Personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations) and individual well-being.

Likewise, while applying regression analysis in order to find the model fit, it was found that, the value of R is less than 0.5 indicating that, there is actually a weak relationship as a whole between independent and dependent variables. Similarly, the value of unstandardized beta highlights that, the 18% change in terms of personality camouflage will possibly be appeared on one unit change in individual well-being. However, negative 2 percent change in terms of controlled freewill has been shown on one unit change in individual well-being implying that, controlled freewill will possibly decrease the individual well-being by 2 percent. Although, almost 26% change in terms of external expectations will possibly appear while applying one unit change on individual well-being. Likewise, while applying regression analysis in order to find the model fit, it was found that, the value of R is less than 0.5 indicating that, there is actually a weak relationship as a whole between independent and dependent variables.

Subsequently, it can be concluded from the above information that, there is a positively significant but weak relationship between social masking and individual well-being. Hence, it can be argued with some certainty that, personality camouflage, controlled freewill and external expectations actually contribute positively in one's well-being as, the social acceptance of social masking provides the solid basis over which, the above argument can be made. On the contrary, social isolation may cause due to the non-acceptance of the general norms and that may eventually results into harming individual well-being in the long run.

5.3 Recommendations

1. The results of this study can be used to find ways and means in order to reduce the negative impacts of social masking
2. This study promotes the idea in the society to accept those individuals who explicitly navigate from the general norms of the society
3. The study provides the basis over which other factors like one's socio-economic status, country, family tree, relationship status and etc. can be included in order to investigate statistically their impact on the individual well-being
4. The study can also help psychologists and other practitioners to provide the right advice to the respective individuals regarding how these factors can help them in their well-being
5. The study can be also be used to analyze the factors like social isolation, loneliness, individual dissatisfaction with current social norms may contribute positively or negatively in individual well-being.

References

- Allport, G.W. (1961). *Pattern and growth in personality*. New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
- Alatartseva, E., & Barysheva, G. (2015). Well-being: subjective and objective aspects. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 166, 36-42.
- Alexander, R., Aragón, O. R., Bookwala, J., Cherbuin, N., Gatt, J. M., Kahrilas, I. J., ... & Styliadis, C. (2021). The neuroscience of positive emotions and affect: Implications for cultivating happiness and wellbeing. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 121, 220-249.
- Chapman, L., Rose, K., Hull, L., & Mandy, W. (2022). "I want to fit in... but I don't want to change myself fundamentally": A qualitative exploration of the relationship between masking and mental health for autistic teenagers. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 99, 102069.
- Cook, J., Hull, L., Crane, L., & Mandy, W. (2021). Camouflaging in autism: A systematic review. *Clinical psychology review*, 89, 102080.
- Crescioni, A. W., Baumeister, R. F., Ainsworth, S. E., Ent, M., & Lambert, N. M. (2016). Subjective correlates and consequences of belief in free will. *Philosophical Psychology*, 29(1), 41-63.

- Didkovskaya, Y. V., & Trynov, D. V. (2019). Social well-being and expectations of the youth in the industrial region. *Economic and social changes: facts, trends, forecast*, 12(1), 202-214.
- Dejonckheere, E., Rhee, J. J., Baguma, P. K., Barry, O., Becker, M., Bilewicz, M., ... & Bastian, B. (2022). Perceiving societal pressure to be happy is linked to poor well-being, especially in happy nations. *Scientific reports*, 12(1), 1514.
- Erevik, E. K., Vedaa, Ø., Pallesen, S., Hysing, M., & Sivertsen, B. (2023). The five-factor model's personality traits and social and emotional loneliness: Two large-scale studies among Norwegian students. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 207, 112115.
- Feldman, G., Baumeister, R. F., & Wong, K. F. E. (2014). Free will is about choosing: The link between choice and the belief in free will. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 55, 239-245.
- Garcia, D. (2006). Determinants of Well-Being: An experimental Study among Adolescents [pdf]. Retrieved from <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:207089/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Goundar, S. (2012). Chapter 3-Research Methodology and Research Method. Cloud Computing. Research Gate Publications.
- González-Hernández, J., López-Mora, C., Portolés-Ariño, A., Muñoz-Villena, A. J., & Mendoza-Díaz, Y. (2017). Psychological well-being, personality and physical activity. One life style for the adult life. *Acción Psicológica*, 14(1), 65-78.
- Gooding, P. (2020). The association between belief in free will, personal control, and life outcomes (Doctoral dissertation, University of Essex).
- Gutiérrez, F., & Valdesoiro, F. (2023). The evolution of personality disorders: A review of proposals. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 14, 1110420.
- Kline, R. B. (2005). Principles and practice of structural equation modeling: Guilford Press.
- Kline, R. B. (2016). Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling. New York: The Guilford Press
- Klein, J., Krahn, R., Howe, S., Lewis, J., McMorris, C., & Macoun, S. (2024). A systematic review of social camouflaging in autistic adults and youth: Implications and theory. *Development and Psychopathology*, 1-15.
- Klein, J., & Macoun, S. J. (2025). Person-environment fit and social camouflaging in autism. *New Ideas in Psychology*, 76, 101112.
- Maslow, A. H. (1968). *Toward a psychology of being* (2nd ed.). New York: Van Nostrand
- Monroe, A. E., & Malle, B. F. (2010). From uncaused will to conscious choice: The need to study, not speculate about people's folk concept of free will. *Review of Philosophy and Psychology*, 1, 211-224.
- Nyuhuan, G. (2023). The Path to Happiness: Freedom from the Shackles of External Expectations. *EPR International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 9(7), 49-55.
- Ofori, D. W., & Bell, J. (2020). Societal expectations and well-being of academics: Views from University lecturers in Ghana. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 33(10), 74-84.
- Pandey, P., & Pandey, M. M. (2015). Research methodology: Tools and techniques.
- Ruggeri, K., Garcia-Garzon, E., Maguire, Á., Matz, S., & Huppert, F. A. (2020). Well-being is more than happiness and life satisfaction: a multidimensional analysis of 21 countries. *Health and quality of life outcomes*, 18, 1-16.
- Robinson, E., Hull, L., & Petrides, K. V. (2020). Big Five model and trait emotional intelligence in camouflaging behaviours in autism. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 152, 109565.
- Rogers, D. S., Duraipappah, A. K., Antons, D. C., Munoz, P., Bai, X., Fragkias, M., & Gutscher, H. (2012). A vision for human well-being: transition to social sustainability. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 4(1), 61-73.
- Rauthmann, J. F. (2021). Capturing interactions, correlations, fits, and transactions: A person-environment relations model. In *The handbook of personality dynamics and processes* (pp. 427-522). Academic Press.

- Scully, C. (2014). *Scully's Medical Problems in Dentistry E-Book: Scully's Medical Problems in Dentistry E-Book*. Elsevier Health Sciences.
- Tov, W. (2018). Well-being concepts and components. In E. Diener, S. Oishi, & L. Tay (Eds.), *Handbook of Well-Being*. Salt Lake City, UT: DEF Publishers. doi: nobascholar.com
- Taylor, S. A., Black, H. G., Donovan, L. A. N., Ishida, C., & Judson, K. (2014). The relationship between eudaimonic well-being and social well-being with millennials. *Journal of Consumer Satisfaction, Dissatisfaction and Complaining Behavior*, 27, 102-117.
- Yunus, M. R. B. M., Wahab, N. B. A., Ismail, M. S., & Othman, M. S. (2018). The importance role of personality trait. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(7), 1028-1036.

